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Ethno-botanical potential of medicinal legumes in the Western Ghats of Karnataka

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ABSTRACT

The present study aims to explore Western Ghats of Karnataka to document the distribution, diversity and ethno botanical knowledge of medicinal legumes. The traditional knowledge of about 28 medicinal plants were recorded from different biogeographic regions of Karnataka. Among the documented medicinal legumes *Kingiodendron pinnatum* is an endangered medicinal plant included in Red Data List of IUCN. Rapid disappearance of medicinal legumes due to overexploitation and urbanization suggests that unrecorded ethno-botanical information may be lost forever. Thus, it is important to document the traditional ecological knowledge of medicinal plants.

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INTRODUCTION

India has a very rich biodiversity, unique physical, ethnic diversity, traditional culture, and much indigenous knowledge or tribal wisdom¹. The documentation of traditional knowledge on the medicinal uses of plants has led to the development of many important drugs of modern day²⁻⁴. Traditional systems of medicine have been in vogue for treating various ailments in many countries such as China, Japan and India since immemorial time⁵⁻⁹. The use of medicinal plants products could be traced back as the beginning of human civilization. The earliest documentation of medicinal plants in Hindu culture or in India is found in “Rigveda”, which is said to have been written between 4500 B.C. and 1600 B.C. and is supposed to be the oldest repository of human knowledge¹⁰. The use of medicinal plants in the treatment of diseases was conceived by tribal people thousands of years ago. The ethnic groups are repositories of the knowledge of herbal medicine. Many tribal groups have been using several plants or animal products for medicinal preparations and these medicines are known as ethno medicine¹¹. In India medicinal plants have long been used to treat different kinds of diseases¹²⁻¹³. Today there is an increasing desire to unravel the role of ethno botanical studies in trapping the centuries old traditional folk knowledge as well as in searching new plant resources of food, drug etc. The study of the tribal knowledge of plants is an important aspect of ethno botanical research. There is virtually no report on this aspect from the state of Karnataka despite the fact that it's Western Ghats belt inhabited by many tribal groups, such as the Siddis, the Gowlis, and the Koragas, the Malekudiyas and Kunbis. The meagre ethnobotanical information from this state is restricted to the medicinal plants used in ayurvedic preparations and to those mentioned in ancient medical scripts^[14]. At present wild useful medicinal plants are highly threatened due to over exploitation, unsustainable harvesting for trade, habitat destruction, human encroachment and application of inappropriate technologies. In view of this an attempt has been made to collect ethnobotanical information on medicinal plants in the Western Ghats region of Karnataka. India.

STUDY AREA AND METHODOLOGY

The Western Ghats of Karnataka lies between 10°10'N 77°04'E. The field exploration was undertaken in Shiradi Ghat, Bisle Ghat and Sigegudda of Hassan district, Gundya, Kukke subramanya of South Canara, Biligiri rangabetta, Gopaldaswami betta of Chamarajanagar district, Kudremukh, Sringeri, Kigga of Chikmagalur and Agumbe of the Shimoga district of Western Ghats of Karnataka.. The study areas harbour diverse types of vegetation beset with evergreen, semi-evergreen, moist, dry deciduous and scrub forests rich in diversity of potential medicinal plants. During the field visits interaction was made with tribal people through interviews and discussion. The information about plants and their distribution, part of plant used for preparation of drugs were documented during the field survey. The

Sr.	Scientific name	Sub family	Part used	Medicinal uses	Distribution
1	<i>Adenanthera pavonia</i> (Linn)	Mimosae	Leaves	Dental disorder	Agumbe
2	<i>Dichrostachys cinerea</i> (Linn)	Mimosae	Leaves	Fever	Agumbe
3	<i>Albizia adianthifolia</i> (Schumach.) W.F. Wight	Mimosae	Bark, Root	River blindness, Alzheimer's diseases	Sringeri, Agumbe, Hassan, Chickmaglore
4	<i>Albizia lebeck</i> (L) Benth	Mimosae	Seed	Snake bite, Dental disorder, Food Poisoning and Wounds	Hassan, Shimoga, Kodagu, Dakshina Kannada, Uttar Kannada.
5	<i>Albizia amara</i> Roxb	Mimosae	Bark, Flower, Seeds	Cough, Skin diseases, Urinary retention, Diarrhea.	Sringeri, Agumbe, Hassan, Chickmaglore
6	<i>Albizia odorrotissima</i> Benth	Mimosae	Bark, Fruit, Flower, Leaves	Allergy, Respiratory disorder, Asthama, Fever	Hassan District, Shiradi, Bisle
7	<i>Cassia biflora</i> (L)	Caesalpineae	Leaves	Medicinal plant	Agumbe
8	<i>Moullava spicata</i> (Dulz). Nicolsen	Caesalpineae	Root, Bark	Skin diseases, pneumonia.	Sringeri, Agumbe.
9	<i>Humboldtia brunonis</i> Wall	Caesalpineae	Leaves, Bark	Arthritis, Diabetes	Shiradi, Bisle Ghats of Karnata
10	<i>Delonox regia</i> Raf.	Caesalpineae	Stem, Bark	Antiviral	Manglore, Shimoga Hassan, Chikmagalur
11	<i>Ceasalpinia</i> <i>mimosoides</i> Lamk.	Caesalpineae	Stem	The tender stem juice mixed with curd and taken internally in the treatment of dysentery	Sringeri, Agumbe Bisle Ghats
12	<i>Caesalpinia</i> <i>pulcherrima</i> (Linn)	Caesalpineae	Leaves, Flower	Skin diseases	Bisle, Shiradi, Agumbe, Sirimane falls
13	<i>Atylosia albicans</i> (Wt.et.Arn.) Benth	Papilionatae	Leaves	Fever	Hassan District
14	<i>Butea frandosa</i> Roxb	Papilionatae	Flower, Root, Seed,	Antiimplantation activity, Diarrhea.	Sringeri, Agumbe, Hassan, Chickmaglore

			Gum		
15	<i>Cassia occidentalis</i> Linn	Papilionatae	Herb or Under shrub- Root, Leaves, Seed.	Cough, Asthma and Skin diseases	Hassan, Shimoga, Kodagu, Dakhshina Kannada(Udupi, Manglore), Uttar Kannada (North Canara) and Belgaum.
16	<i>Cassia tora</i> Linn	Papilionatae	Leaves	Ringworm, Skin diseases	Hassan, shimoga, Kodagu, dakhshina kannada (Udupi, Manglore), Uttar kannada (North canara) and Belgaum
17	<i>Cassia hirsuta</i> (L).H.S	Papilionatae	Root	Digestive disorder	Sringeri, Agumbe, Hassan, Chickmaglore
18	<i>Cassia sophera</i> Linn	Papilionatae	Root, stem, bark, seed	Ringworm, Purgative	Manglore, Shimoga Hassan, Chikmagalur.
19	<i>Dalbergia latifolia</i> (Roxb)	Papilionatae	Leaves	Antimicrobial	Agumbe
20	<i>Derris scandens</i> Benth	Papilionatae	Root, Bark	Snake bite	Shiradi, Bisle Ghats of Karnataka
21	<i>Derris species</i>	Papilionatae	leaves	Fever	Bisle Ghat
22	<i>Desmodium gangeticum</i> Lamk	Papilionatae	Root, Bark, Seed	Tumours, Fever	Shiradi, North Canera.
23	<i>Flemingia bracteata</i> Roxb	Papilionatae	Roor, Leaves	Tetanus	Shiradi, Bisle Ghats of Karnataka
24	<i>Kingiodendron</i> <i>pinnatum</i> Rox.Hams	Papilionatae	Bark	Sores in elephants, Genito-urinary infection	Shiradi Ghats
25	<i>Mucuna pruriens</i> (L).DC	Papilionatae	Leaves, Seeds	Used to cure Parkinson's diseases , Anti- cataleptic activity	Agumbe
26	<i>Tephrosia tinctoria</i> L.C	Papilionatae	Leaves, Root	Antimicrobial	Chikmagalur, Coorg Hassan district
27	<i>Xylia xylocarpa</i> (Roxb)	Papilionatae	Leaves	Skin diseases	Agumbe
28	<i>Zornia gibbosa</i> Span. in Linnaea	Papilionatae	Leaves	Inflamation	Hassan District

ethno medicinal plants were collected from the forest areas with the help of folk practitioner's and identified taxonomically using the floras, already identified specimens and in consultation with taxonomist. A few plants were photographed and collected for preparing herbaria and voucher specimens were deposited in the Biodiversity Conservation Laboratory, Department of Environmental Science, University of Mysore.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This study indicates that the tribal people of Western Ghats of Karnataka have acquired considerable knowledge about the medicinal plants. Data and information obtained from the present investigation regarding the medicinal legume species, parts used, and distribution are compiled and shown in Table.1. Different plant parts were used to cure asthma, allergy, dental disorder, respiratory disorder, vomiting, fever, snake bite, cough, skin diseases, diabetics, arthritis, Alzheimer's diseases, diarrhoea, ringworm and digestive disorder (Table. 1). Phytomedicine has long been recognized as one of the oldest forms of remedies used by humans¹⁵⁻¹⁶. Many people in developing countries still rely on traditional healing practices using medicinal plants for their daily healthcare needs, in spite of the advancement in modern medicine¹⁷. There is abundant undocumented traditional knowledge of herbal remedies used to treat various diseases in many countries including India. Traditional healers use their five senses to diagnose the diseases, which are remarkable because they live in interior areas and lack the use of modern scientific equipment's for treatment; however, they treat diseases using medicinal plants and animals¹⁸. Documentation of such plants and animals from the perspective of ethno biological angle is important for the understanding of indigenous knowledge systems. These resources are genetically important for future research. In the present study a total of 28 medicinal legume species are recorded. Although all parts of various plants species are used in traditional medication of various diseases, leaves are mainly used. The utilization and administration of medicinal legumes depend on type of disease. The most frequently used method was decoction of plant parts homogenised in water. *Kingiodendron pinnatum* an endangered medicinal plant is used for treating gonorrhoea, catarrhal conditions of genito-urinary and respiratory tracts and having antioxidant activity¹⁹. *Humboldtia brunonis* traditionally used to cure diabetes. *Ceasalpinia mimmosoides*, *Zornia gibbosa*, *Xylia xylocarpa*, *Albizia lebbeck*, *Moullava spicata*, *Derris scandens*, *Desmodium gangeticum*, *Tephrosia tinctoria* were used to treat tumours, fever, snake bite, skin diseases etc. The tribes of Western Ghats have vast knowledge of herbal treatments for a wide range of physical ailments²⁰. Different parts of plants like flowers, roots, rhizome, inflorescence, fruits, seeds, bark, leaves, gum etc., are being used for different purposes. The information and findings presented are primarily based on the interviews with the tribal medicinal practitioners and the local people from the investigated area. The data obtained in this study suggests

that ethno-botanical data can be used as an indicator of pharmaceutical potential of the collected medicinal legume species. Future investigations into the pharmacological importance of such plants their diversity and phytochemistry may add new knowledge of information to the traditional medicinal and cultural systems of the Western Ghats of Karnataka. The study has shown that continuous exploitation of several medicinal legumes such as *Kingiodendron pinnatum*, *Derris scandens* etc., from the wild and substantial loss of their habitats has resulted in the rapid decline of these species in the Western Ghats of Karnataka. The data offers basic information to the pharmaceutical industries for further research in the treatment and control of ailments.

CONCLUSION

The results of our study have shown the persistence of folk medicine practices in Western Ghats of Karnataka and that the people are still dependent on indigenous knowledge for health care that are being influenced by culture and socioeconomic aspects, providing a cheaper and accessible alternative to the high cost pharmaceutical remedies. The possible benefit of plant-derived bioactive compounds is a rewarding area of research, particularly in countries such as India which have a rich biodiversity coupled with a high prevalence and variety of infectious diseases. Present study revealed that 28 medicinal plants of Western Ghats of Karnataka are used in preparations of various classic and traditional medicines. It is the need of the hour to conserve all such potential ayurvedic medicinal legumes for the future by *ex-situ* and *in-situ* conservation methods. It is necessary to characterize the active principles involved in control of various diseases and use them as markers to avoid adulteration, identify and authenticate the genuine crude drug for various medicinal properties.

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